

EPIDEMIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF AIDS AND ORGANIZATION OF EPIDEMIOLOGICAL SURVEILLANCE

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Relevance of the research: According to the World Health Organization, approximately 88.4 million people worldwide have been infected with AIDS since the beginning of the epidemic, and 42.3 million of them have died. According to the United Nations, AIDS/HIV ranks as the 5th leading cause of death among diseases today. The number of people living with the disease exceeds 39.9 million globally. Women account for 44% of those infected with AIDS, while the remaining percentage are men. Worldwide, 86% of infected individuals are aware that they have contracted HIV, while the rest continue to live without knowing their status.

Like in other countries around the world, the number of HIV infections is increasing among the population in Uzbekistan as well. In 2024, it was reported that more than 48,000 people in the country were living with AIDS. Among them, 55% are men, 45% are women, and 14% are children under the age of 18. By 2023, the number of people infected with AIDS had exceeded 48,000. Over the past five years, the number of HIV tests has increased fivefold, from 700,000 to 3.5 million. The government has allocated 80% of the funding for medications.

Research objective: Improving the effectiveness of AIDS diagnosis and describing the modern trends of the epidemic.

Research materials and methods: The official reports on AIDS infection for 2023–2024 from the Bukhara Regional Department of Sanitary and Epidemiological Well-being and Public Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the 2023–2024 official reports from the Bukhara Regional AIDS Prevention Center, were used along with epidemiological and statistical methods.

Research results: The average risk of HIV transmission is as follows: 90% through blood transfusion; 25% from mother to child at birth without treatment, reduced to 1–2% with antiretroviral therapy; 0.67% through injectable drug use; 0.30% through percutaneous needle injury; and 0.03–3% through sexual contact.

Conclusion: State programs aimed at combating AIDS have strengthened the material and technical base of medical institutions, which has helped reduce the rate of HIV transmission through parenteral routes. Measures have also been implemented to prevent mother-to-child transmission of the infection. Every pregnant woman is placed under medical supervision at a local healthcare facility starting from the 14th week of pregnancy and undergoes an HIV screening. If HIV is detected in a pregnant woman, she is provided with special antiviral prophylactic medications from the time of diagnosis until childbirth. The newborn also receives antiviral prophylactic treatment for one month. As a result, the rate of mother-to-child transmission has significantly decreased.

To eliminate the HIV epidemic by 2030, achieving the “95-95-95” strategy by 2025 is essential. According to the “95-95-95” principle, 95% of people living with HIV should be aware of their status, 95% of diagnosed patients should receive specialized therapy, and 95% of treated patients should achieve a low viral load by 2025, ultimately aiming to eliminate AIDS transmission by 2030. Promoting a healthy lifestyle among the population, explaining the modes of disease transmission and risk factors, raising awareness about the negative consequences of prostitution and drug addiction, ensuring the use of single-use syringes and gloves by medical personnel, implementing proper laboratory testing for donors, strictly adhering to regulations when receiving blood and blood substitutes, and providing patients with antiretroviral drugs are crucial measures to prevent the spread of HIV.